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EAR ANALYSIS OF WINTER WHEAT AND BARLEY IN FIELD AND VEGETATION EXPERIMENTS DEPENDING ON THE APPLICATION OF ORGANOMINERAL FERTILIZERS

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Abstract

The structural elements of ears of winter wheat variety "Nairi 68" and barley variety "Ara" have been studied using equivalent doses of organic and mineral fertilizers in field and vegetation experiments. The regularity of ear indicators between different biological research methods has been revealed, and the clear effect of organomineral fertilizers is mainly expressed on the number and weight of grains in the ear, which provide an increase in yield compared to the control.

Keywords: Winter wheat and barley - organomineral fertilizers - ear analysis - harvest

One of the characteristic varietal differences of cereal crops, by means of which the potential for yield and grain quality can be preliminary revealed, is certainly the structural analysis of the ears, on the basis of which the further fate of the variety is decided. It is important to compare the data from such analyzes with the mineral nutrition of plants, when analyzing ears of cereal crops, because ensuring high yields of any variety is directly related to maintenance of a rational system of soil-plant-fertilizer. In the view of this approach, the involvement of winter wheat varieties "Nairi 68" and barley "Ara" in our field and vegetation experiments with the application of equivalent doses of organic and mineral fertilizers can clarify the relationship between varietal potential and mineral nutrition to a certain extent.

The primary description of the genetic bases and analysis of the ears of the bred varieties of wheat "Nairi 68" and barley "Ara" were carried out by the authors themselves - the breeders [6, 22]. Studies on revealing the comparative yield of about 20 varieties of the world collection of winter wheat, including the released varieties Bezostaya 1, Umanka, Nairi 68, Akhtamar, in rainfed conditions of the Zangezur agricultural zone showed that the yield of Nairi 68 on the background of mineral fertilizers $N_{120}P_{120}K_{120}$ kg/ha surpassed all other varieties and amounted to 30-35 c/ha [18, 19]. In the rainfed conditions of the Sevan basin, from crops of 5 varieties of winter soft wheat (Bezostaya 1, Mironovskaya 808, Ani, Nairi 68, W-301) at seeding rates of 260, 280 and 300 kg/ha, "Nairi 68" provided a higher yield - 32.6-39.2 c/ha with a seeding rate of 280 kg/ha [17].

On the irrigated soils of Ararat Plain and Shirak zone, the study of ear structure and the degree of yield of numerous varieties of the world collection of winter wheat, the results of which were compared with the Bezostaya 1 variety, showed the advantage of this variety in total indicators, and the yield of individual varieties varied between 48 - 70 c/ha [8,20,23]. On the meadow-brown irrigated soils of Ararat Plain, mineral fertilizers at a dose of $N_{120}P_{60}K_{60}$ kg/ha without crop rotation provided winter wheat yield of Bezostaya 1 variety 35 c/ha

and 60.1 c/ha in the 7th field crop rotation, crude protein in grain was 15.8% [3, 5]. Experiments have established that the best sowing time for winter wheat variety 'Armenianka 60' variety on meadow-brown irrigated soils is the first decade of October, the yield, depending on the sowing rate (3.0, 4.5 and 6 million /ha of seeds) ranges from 51.3 to 57.4 c/ha [12].

Interesting studies conducted on winter wheat varieties of the world collection of VIR on the ratio of grain to straw have shown that the highest yield is produced by low-stem varieties (stem height 70 - 85 cm), where the percentage of grain in production biomass (grain - straw) is 36.6 - 42.2%, and for medium-stem (90-105 cm) and high-stem (110 - 125 cm) varieties, respectively 28.6 - 34.4 and 22.2 - 26.3% [17]

Mineral fertilizers in doses up to $N_{100}P_{90}K_{80}$ kg/ha and separately N_{90} (60+30 fertilizing) significantly increase the yield and quality of winter wheat grain in different soil and climatic conditions [9, 10, 15]. With the combined application of 20t/ha of manure and $N_{150}P_{90}K_{90}$ kg/ha, the winter hardiness of winter wheat increased by 9.5%, the weight of 1000 grains increased by 1.2 - 3.4%, the number of grains per ear increased by 11.9 - 16.9%, and the yield increase was 24.7 c/ha [4]. At high temperatures (38.8°C), the first-class winter wheat grain is formed, where the protein is 15.2 - 17.6; gluten is 38.9 - 43%, natural is 818 - 826 g/l [14]. Studies conducted on 57 malting varieties of winter barley showed that they provide a high yield despite different winter conditions [16].

In the analysis of ears of cereal crops, the ear density, which characterizes the density of the spikelets in the ears is important. This trait is associated with the hereditary features of the variety and is a rather constant value for it [11].

The aim of the present research is to study important biological indicators in the ear structure of winter wheat variety "Nairi 68" and winter barley variety "Ara" when using mineral fertilizers, biohumus and semi-fermented manure, to find the relationship between these indicators and plant yield, as well as to reveal the regularity between the results of field and vegetation experiments.

Material and methodology. Field and vegetation experiments were carried out in 2020-2022 on the varieties of winter wheat "Nairi 68" and winter barley "Ara" at Etchmiadzin production and experimental farm of the Scientific Center for Agriculture, on typical brown irrigated meadow soils. The experiments were carried out in 4-fold repetition (each repetition in field experiments was 50 m², in vegetation experiments - 1 vessel). Schemes of experiments are shown in Tables 2 and 3, where the principles of single difference and comparison between the options were preserved. In field experiments, the sowing rate of wheat was 250 kg/ha (about 4.2 - 4.5 million grains), and barley was 200 kg/ha (4.0 - 4.5 million grains), with 25 grains in vegetation vessels. Phosphorus - potassium fertilizers of 40% nitrogen

Fig.1 Vegetation experiments

Harvesting was carried out in the experiments in the first decade of July and was taken into account by the weight method. At the same time, 10 medium-sized full ears were taken from each replication for ear analysis. Ammonium nitrate, granulated superphosphate (P₂O₅ - 19.5%), potassium salt (K₂O - 60%), from organic - semi-rotted cattle manure (N - 0.48; P₂O₅ - 0.23 and K₂O - 0.55% nitrogen dose) and biohumus (N - 1.8 - 2, 0; P₂O₅ - 0.85 - 2.0 and K₂O - 0.51 - 0.73% according to the certificate - nitrogen doses) were used as mineral fertilizers. Chemical weed control was carried out in April in field experiments and weeding was carried out in the vegetation experiments.

Laboratory soil analyzes were carried out according to generally accepted methods [1, 13], in which the mechanical composition of the soil was determined by the classical pipette method and assessed according to the gradation of N.A. Kachinsky [8], hygroscopic moisture - by the gravimetric method, p^H of the water extract - by a potentiometer, humus - by I.V. Tyurin, total nitrogen - by the Kjeldahl method, mobile forms of nitrogen - by I.V. Tyurin and M.M. Kononova, and phosphorus and potassium - by Machigin method. Statistical processing of yield data was carried out by the method of dispersion analysis [7].

were applied to the soil in the fall for plowing (field experiments) and into vegetation vessels at a depth of 7 - 8 cm (October 20 - 25), and 60% nitrogen was applied in the spring in the form of top dressing in the 1st and the 3rd decades of April. The seeds were sown on October 27-28. In field experiments, 4 irrigations were carried out (in the fall - immediately after sowing, in the 2nd decade of April, in the second decade of May and in the first decade of June with an irrigation rate of 900 m³ / ha). Artesian water from Ararat Plain is used, the irrigation rate is 3600 m³/ha. In vegetation experiments, 40 - 44 liters of drinking water per vessel were used during the vegetative season.

Fig.2 Field experiments

Results and Discussion. The Ararat Plain is the most active agricultural region of Armenia. According to average annual data, the sum of active temperatures (above 10⁰C) per year reaches 4000-4300⁰C (average + 10.6⁰C), in winter the absolute minimum temperature reaches 30, -35⁰C, the amount of precipitation is 200 - 260 mm, humidity coefficient according to Shashko is 0.20-0.25 [21]. The scientific center of agriculture is located almost in the center of Ararat Plain at an altitude of 853 m above sea level, and its land areas are presented as a homogeneous plain. From this territory, an area of 5 hectares was selected for field experiments, in the center of which one soil section by genetic horizons was conducted (Table 1). The soil for vegetation experiments was taken from the arable layer (horizon A 0-30 cm) of the field plot.

Table 1 shows that the soil of the experimental plot is rather thick (A + B = 81 cm), and the mechanical composition is estimated as medium loamy (physical clay in horizons A - 35.09; B₂ - 33.40%) and heavy loamy (B₁ - 59.92%). The mechanical composition is light loamy in horizon C. The reaction of the soil environment is alkaline (p^H - 7.6 - 8.4), the content of humus and total nitrogen is low, which is due to the intense mineralization of organic matter at high soil temperatures during the vegetation season. As for the mobile forms of the main nutrients, they have an average content according to the corresponding gradations.

Table 1.

Physical-mechanical and agrochemical characterization test plot soils

Genetic horizons and depth, cm	Hydrosopic moisture, %	Amount < 0,01 m particles (physical clay), %	pH water extract	Humus, %	Total N, %	Mobile forms, mg per 100 g of soil		
						N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
A 0-30	4,5	35,09	7,9	1,85	0,20	4,5	2,6	36
B ₁ 30-57	3,5	59,92	7,6	1,12	0,08	4,2	2,8	25
B ₂ 57-81	4,4	33,40	8,3	0,78	0,05	3,5	1,9	21
C 81-106	2,3	22,60	8,4	0,45	0,03	1,7	1,6	16

In order not to overload the article with tables, the average data from field and vegetation experiments on yield and analysis of ears for 3 years were presented (Tables 2 and 3). Table 2 shows that the wheat grain yield in the variant control of field experiments averaged 49.5 over three years, and in the fertilized variants were 63.0 - 67.9 c/ha, with the best performance of variants N₁₂₀P₈₀K₉₀, N₁₂₀K₉₀ and biohumus was 6t/ha. Sim-

ilar data in these options for barley also had an advantage. For all the years of research, the yield of wheat and barley in all fertilized variants, including the average for three years was reliable (NSR₀₅ for wheat = 2.43; for barley - 1.67 c/ha). The table also shows that under the influence of mineral and organic fertilizers, the parameters in wheat and barley ears change positively within small limits.

Table 2.

Results of yield and ear analysis of winter and barley depending on organomineral fertilizers (field experiments, average for 2020 – 2022)

Crop	Experimental options	Yield, c/ha	Length of one ear, cm	Weight of one ear, g.	Number of spikelets in one ear, pcs.	Number of grains in one ear, pcs.	Weight of grains of one ear, g.
Wheat	1.No fertilizer (control)	49,5	8,8	2,8	19,6	47,0	2,2
	2.N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ K ₉₀ -kg/ha	67,9	9,9	3,6	24,2	57,9	3,4
	3. N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	63,3	9,5	3,2	22,0	54,8	2,5
	4. N ₁₂₀ K ₉₀	65,9	9,6	3,3	2,10	55,4	2,6
	5.Biohumus-6 t/ha	64,2	10,4	4,4	22,7	56,4	3,4
	6.Manure -25t/ha	63,0	9,3	3,7	20,9	55,3	3,2
	Sx, % HCP ₀₅ , c	1,24 2,43	-	-	-	-	-
Barley	1. No fertilizer (control)	45,7	5,5	2,5	14,5	48,2	2,3
	2.N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ K ₉₀ -kg/ha	65,1	6,8	3,6	18,5	56,2	2,7
	3. N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	62,2	5,4	2,6	17,7	52,6	2,4
	4. N ₁₂₀ K ₉₀	63,0	5,5	2,6	19,2	53,2	2,4
	5.Biohumus-6 t/ha	64,9	6,6	2,8	19,6	55,9	2,7
	6.Manure -25t/ha	63,1	6,4	2,6	17,6	51,2	2,3
	Sx, % HCP ₀₅ , c	0,87 1,67	-	-	-	-	-

Among these parameters, the number and average weight of grains in one ear are important, which determines the real grain yield. As it can be seen from Table 2, in the variant without fertilizers for wheat, the average number of grains in one ear is 47 pieces (pcs), and the weight is 2.2 g. In fertilized variants, these data range from 54.8 (N₁₂₀P₈₀) to 57.9 pcs. (N₁₂₀P₈₀K₉₀) and 2.5 - 3.4 g. In the control variant of barley, the average number and average weight of grains in one ear are 48.2

pcs. and 2.3 g, and in fertilized versions it is 51.2 - 56.2 pcs. and 2.3 - 2.7 g, respectively. It should also be noted that there is no big difference in the number and weight of grains in one ear of wheat and barley, which is also proven by yield data. The real difference in yield in fertilized plant variants is also directly related to the increase in the total number of ears, due to which an increase in yield is formed compared to the control.

Table 3.

Results of yield and ear analysis of wheat and barley in the dependence on organomineral fertilizers (vegetative experiments, average for 2020- 2022)

Crop	Experimental options	Yield, g/vessel	Length of one ear, cm	Weight of one ear, g.	Number of spikelets in one ear, pcs.	Number of grains in one ear, pcs.	Weight of grains of one ear, g.
Wheat	1.No fertilizer (control)	9,3	7,9	1,5	18,3	26,1	1,0
	2.N _{1,95} P _{1,3} K _{1,56} g/vessel	16,1	9,2	2,9	23,8	38,7	1,9
	3. N _{1,95} P _{1,3}	15,0	8,2	2,2	21,8	35,3	1,4
	4. N _{1,95} K _{1,56}	15,4	9,1	2,7	20,1	38,2	1,5
	5.Biohumus-87 g/vessel	15,1	8,6	3,2	19,6	39,1	2,2
	6.Manure-390 g/vessel	14,4	8,3	2,7	18,9	38,0	1,7
	Sx,% HCP ₀₅ , g	5,63 2,52	-	-	-	-	-
Barley	1. No fertilizer (control)	9,0	4,4	1,4	14,3	24,8	1,1
	2.N _{1,95} P _{1,3} K _{1,56} g/vessel	11,9	5,9	1,7	18,7	30,3	1,5
	3. N _{1,95} P _{1,3}	11,0	4,4	1,5	16,9	27,1	1,2
	4. N _{1,95} K _{1,56}	11,6	4,5	1,6	16,6	25,2	1,3
	5.Biohumus-87 g/vessel	12,4	5,8	1,7	17,9	29,0	1,5
	6.Manure-390 g/vessel	11,1	5,6	1,6	17,2	26,3	1,4
	Sx,% HCP ₀₅ , g	2,14 0,76	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3 shows similar results of vegetation experiments, where a certain identity of the structural units of the ears with the data of field experiments is observed. The average length of one ear according to the experimental variants of wheat varies within 7.9-9.2 cm, the average weight is 1.5-2.9 g, the average number of spikelets per ear is 18.3-23.8 pieces, the number of grains in one ear is 26.1-39.1; and their weight is 1.0-1.9 g, with small numbers referring to the control, and large ones are N_{1,95}P_{1,3}K_{1,56} g/vessel. The same dynamics is observed between the variants in barley, but significantly at a lower level. As for the grain yield of plants, for wheat this figure was 30% higher than the barley yield on average over three years. The wheat yield according to the experimental variants ranged from 9.3 (control) to 16.1 g (N_{1,95}P_{1,3}K_{1,56} g/vessel) and for barley it ranged from 9.0 (control) to 12.4 g (biohumus). In the fertilized variants of the growing season experiments with wheat and barley, the yield compared to the control was significant (NSR05 for wheat = 2.52; and for barley – 0.76 g).

Thus, the genetic features of the ear indicators of winter wheat "Nairi 68" and winter barley "Ara" are quite stable and almost similar when cultivated in field conditions and in vegetation vessels. The influence of organomineral fertilizers on the structural parameters of ears is mainly clearly expressed in the quality and weight of grains in the ear, which determines the increase in yield in these variants compared to the control.

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